

Implementation of Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) in Rahim Yar Khan: Subject Teachers' Vantage

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Abstract

The current study is an investigation of the Implementation of CLIL: Subject Teachers' Perspective. The purpose behind the study is to detect if English is helping to bring out the best of the subjects' understanding amongst the students or is it marginalizing the teachers' ability in describing the fundamental concepts of the target subjects thus compromising curriculum achievement goals. For appropriate results and understand the phenomena, an exploratory research method was used. A need analysis questionnaire was developed in light of the review and experts' opinions. A total of 100 questionnaires were distributed for data collection in primary and secondary schools' teachers out of which 100 were returned. Data examined with frequency, percentage, ANOVA, T.Test in SPSS 20 sheet. The results revealed that the implementation of CLIL lacks appropriate techniques for which some suggestions have been proposed at the end.

Introduction

In order to promote foreign contact, English has been in the world, the global and dominant language, mainly due to colonisation and imperialism (Rao, 2019). It serves as an ELF (Lingua franca) for foreign contact between individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds. In several Countries including Singapore, India, Pakistan and Bangladesh, especially those that were former British colonies, English works a variety of roles, such as an official language and a primary language for schooling (Klein & Wikan, 2019; Kwet, 2019). English, as a primary language used in school, has been made a requirement for the academic and career advancement of learners in countries such as Pakistan, India and Bangladesh.

In 1835 (Evans, 2002), In the Indian subcontinent, Colonial masters introduced English education and the use of English in education persisted until Pakistan's Independence in 1947. Mumtaz, Saqulain, and Mumtaz (2021) found that English proficiency makes it possible and helps to offer luxury to Pakistan's ruling class. As a result, Pakistan has adopted multilingual learning measures to promote the transmission of native languages, national languages and the English language. Whilst also Pakistan's 1973 Constitution says that English should be substituted in education with Urdu, because of their stacks, the ruling class rejects substituting English (Shamim, 2011), as they have prospects to raise their offspring in English.

Area that is both wide and interdisciplinary is addressed by the study of bilingualism. Bilingualism is the practice and use in the classroom of two languages simultaneously and how it can impact the study of a foreign language (Méndez García & Pavón Vázquez, 2012). Since bilingualism evolves and is reflected in positioned social categories, as it is appropriate to understand the outcomes, there may be mention of social dimensions of bilingualism (Wei, 2020). As a human phenomenon or a social phenomenon, bilingualism may be addressed Hamers and Blanc use the word "bilinguality" to indicate the need for two languages by an individual and reserve "bilingualism" to research how two or more languages work in a given community (Hamers, Blanc, & Blanc, 2000). They do not though, indicate that it is plausible to see one of them separated from the other, figuring out their interdependence, saying: It is important to approach bilingualism as a dynamic concept that respectively means the state of bilinguality of persons and the condition of interaction between languages at the common stage. It is however crucial to know this phenomena at different analysis levels: Team work, with in groups and with in society human behaviour. There are some theoretical disciplinary limitations to bilingualism, although these various fields prefer to research different contexts of it. (Baker, 1988)

English as Lingua Franca:

In order to promote foreign contact, English has become the global and dominant language in the world, largely because of colonisation and globalization (Mufwene, 2002). The English language in Pakistan retains emblematic significance but for its connection with Colonial oppression and the rulers since liberation (Ashcroft, Griffiths, & Tiffin, 2003).

In an attempt to meet the global demands of recruitment that requires a lingua franca and also to satisfy the social supremacy needs that accompany speakers of English (Kubota, 2018), most institutes in Pakistan have implemented the teaching of the content subject in English. (Shamim, 2008)

Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) refers to an approach to teaching and studying a subject in a second or foreign language, that requires a part of the whole subject curriculum (Do Coyle, 2007).

CLIL in Rahim Yar Khan:

Rahim Yar Khan is an underdeveloped city of the biggest province of Pakistan, Punjab. The struggle for quality education in this city has brought in a lot of private schools offering O-Levels. These institutes try their best to recruit highly qualified subject specialists. However, most of these subject specialists lack fluency and grip over English, the medium of instruction they are supposed to use in the classroom. A very few teachers can receive the proper training of delivering instructions in English for other subjects) approach to teaching subjects, using English as an instructional tool and responses.

The results of the research shed light on problems faced by non-English teachers forced to teach their subject using English as an instruction medium. Furthermore, the research will help to suggest what remedies can be employed to aid these teachers to overcome their language difficulties.

Literature Review:

The origin of the CLIL approach can be traced to the late 1990s by some experts of the field of education (Brown & Bradford, 2014). Upon comparing this approach with the immersion approach in second language teaching, CLIL appears to be a more realistic solution to the linguistic demands in Europe (Lorenzo, 2007).

CLIL is a diverse and vibrant approach in which the students, as well as teachers, get involved in active practices (Smit & Dafouz, 2012). CLIL is essentially a student-oriented approach, where the teacher and the student engage equally and fully in the learning process (Sulistyo, Rachmajanti, Suharyadi, & Muniroh, 2017).

CLIL stands for Integrated Learning of Content and Vocabulary, but separate perceptions of the approach remain popular as well (Dalton-Puffer, 2008). CLIL is a methodology of language development that originated in the mid-1990s in circumstances where topics or sections of subjects are taught with dual-focused aims, specifically content learning, using a foreign language (Morton, 2016).

Together with the European Commission, CLIL was initiated in 1994 by David Marsh and Anne Maljers as a technique close to language immersion and content-based teaching (Lyster, 2007).

Sum up, it is a performance approach to the issue in which an alternative vocabulary is used for both language and content learning and teaching. The aim of this technique is to foster both content and language skills, while the international language produces non-language information (Tedick & Cammarata, 2012). Since 1996, it has been used to refer to "the combination of teaching the substance of a subject with second language instruction" (Pokrivčáková, 2013; Tedick & Cammarata, 2012). For many educational approaches that include "immersion, plurilingual education, language showers and enhanced services of language", CLIL can be used as an umbrella term (Ball, Kelly, & Clegg, 2016).

Types of CLIL:

Soft CLIL: In the Soft Knowledge and Communication Combined Learning Course, the primary purpose of the class is to concentrate on the meaning of the subject, not the primary goal of the class (Dorothy Coyle, Hood, & Marsh, 2010).

In comparison to this challenging Material and Language Combined Learning, more emphasis is given to the subject's material and language is at the back of the lesson's concentration.

Hard CLIL: The key focus of the CLIL Approach is to improve and strengthen the second-language learning experience of diverse learners. Secondly, it helps and strengthens the knowledge of the subject matter of the discipline. The topics are often portrayed in the additional language of the students as well as in their original language (Leontjev & DeBoer, 2020)

Methodology:

The analysis employed a research design with a mixed-method. When both quantitative and qualitative approaches are often used, according to (Creswell, 2011) they result in a clearer understanding and interpretation of the study challenge. In the context of study, the incorporation of both modes of investigation proved effective in providing a better image of the problem under study. In gaining information in an analytical setting, quantitative analysis techniques are known to be extremely accurate (Kreuger & Neuman, 2006). Similarly, qualitative techniques of study were used to capture the perspective of students, their depth of emotion, and teaching and learning experience (Yilmaz, 2013).

Population: The participants of this research study are the teachers from various private schools of Rahim Yar Khan.

Sample: The survey consisted of 100 teachers for such a report. The researcher based the above learning as the means to select the sampling technique to be "Purposeful Sampling" that entails the availability of knowledgeable persons willing to participate in the research.

Research Tool:

To pre-test semi-structured interviews, thirty interviews were conducted. In this process to make the questionnaire more simple and reliable, only the language and structure of some of the questions were substituted. Much of the fieldwork was performed over a period of one year. In Rahim Yar Khan, Pakistan, researchers began compiling their data from November 2019 to November 2020. Owing to the condition of Covid19, the researcher had to contact respondents via emails and email to perform the survey, the collecting of data was most complicated. It was only after the reopening of the schools those physical interviews and consultations with the respondents took place. The data after collection was processed through SPSS 20.

Results:

Table 1: Teachers' Perception about students' learning language through subject content effectively.

S no.	Level Agreement of	Totally Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Slightly Agree	Totally Agree
S5	F	0	21	21	48	10
	%	0	21	21	48	10
S6	F	0	11	20	39	30
	%	0	11	20	39	30
S7	F	16	41	20	23	0
	%	16	41	20	23	0
S10	F	11	43	3	43	0
	%	11	43	3	43	0
S11	F	16	38	23	10	13
	%	16	38	23	10	13
S12	F	39	14	15	30	2
	%	39	14	15	30	2
S13	F	0	10	13	59	13
	%	0	10	13	59	13
S14	F	8	23	56	13	0
	%	8	23	56	13	0

Note: Only the most frequently used values are discussed in the interpretation.

The results of Table 1 show descriptive statistics of every statement revealing teacher participants' views about different teaching and language skills of teachers influencing students' learning capabilities in English language through subject content. About (48+10)58% agreed that it is more convenient to teach the subject in Urdu. About (39+30)69% agreed that the class discussion done in Urdu proves to be more fruitful in clearing the concept of students while teaching the content in class. About (16+41)57% disagreed that discussions are fruitful in English. About (40+11)51% agreed that they use English for teaching in classroom. About (43+43)43% slightly agreed that they agreed in strong English skills, another major number seen here was 43% of teachers who neither agreed nor disagreed to this statement, possibly due to fear of being penalized by the school management. About (38)38% confessed to their poor listening skill in English. About (39)39% agreed speaking skill is very poor where as 30% claimed that their English speaking skill is good. About (59+18)77% agreed that they have very good reading skill. About (23+56)79% agreed that they possess poor to okay writing English skill.

Table 2: Gender based perception of teachers about students' learning

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t-value	P-Value
Male	48	24.3125	3.44041	.49658	.040	.968
Female	52	24.2885	2.50753	.34773		

In table 2 the significant p-value .0968 ($p < 0.05$) shows that there is no significant difference between the mean score of male ($M=24.3125, SD= 3.44041$) and female ($M=24.2885, SD= 2.50753$). The male as well as female teachers believe that their language skill influences the learning of English language through subject content among their students.

Table 3: Academic Qualification based perception of teachers about students' learning

Teachers' Academic Qualification	N	Mean	Std. deviation	SEM	SQ	df	MS	F	Sig
Intermediate	3	23.0000	2.00000	1.15470	49.350	4	12.337	1.416	.235
Bachelors	28	25.6429	3.32459	.62829	827.650	95	8.712		
Masters	67	23.8358	2.73915	.33464	877.000	99			
PHD	2	23.0000	1.41421	1.00000					

Table 3 exhibits the attitude of teachers by education level of teachers about learning of language through subject content. Results verified that the teachers have similar views regarding their education level having an impact on their students ($df=4, F=1.416, p=.235$). The mean results reveal the teachers having intermediate, masters and Ph.d have a similar opinion about learning of language through subject content.

Table 4: Subject specialization based perception of teachers about student learning

Teachers' Subject Specialization	N	Mean	Std. deviation	SEM	SQ	df	MS	F	Sig
History/Geography	25	24.0000	2.00000	3.14907	15.529	3	5.176	.577	.632
Mathematics	27	24.0741	3.20967	.61770	861.471	96	8.974		
Science/Biology	27	24.2222	2.53185	.48725					
Any other	21	25.0476	3.07370	.67074					

Table 4 exhibits the attitude of teachers having the subject specialization about learning of language through subject content. Results verified that the teachers have similar views regarding their education level having an impact on their students ($df=3, F=.577, p=.632$). The mean results reveal the teachers having major in History/Geography, Mathematics and Science/ Biology subjects have a similar opinion about learning of language through subject content.

Discussion and Conclusion:

It was an exploratory study and basic aim was to investigate extent to which language learning is achieved through subject content or better known as CLIL. After analyzing the data, the conclusions are derived on the basis of findings of the questionnaire. The data reveals many important findings for further improvement in teachers own language and teaching skill for effective learning. It has been analyzed from the data received that teachers' own perception about the language in which the material exists plays an important role in their students learning of language through the subject content. It was found that teachers' training and awareness of the target language is of extreme importance. However, it was revealed through the received data that many teachers are still hesitant in the explanation of subject content in English, the target language which ultimately results in their students' hesitation in communication and usage of the language. It was found that even the teachers who were well equipped academic and technical specialization to teach the subject could not impart knowledge effectively.

Recommendations:

- 1: Firstly, a suggestion about ways to overcome issues that exist with gaps in classroom linguistic skills. The structured application of scaffolding is a method to create directions understandable to low-competency learners.
- 2: In accordance with this, Harmer(2001) proposed that team constellations should also be taken into account in activities that enable learners to work together(Harmer, 2001; Şentürk, 2015). Teachers may team up weak with strong students, depending on the assignment. This has the benefit of being able to get a better grasp of the language for stronger students, while poorer students benefit from the assistance.
- 3: As (Harmer, 2001)emphasized, the linguistic complicatedness of the resources should be adjusted to the specific requirements of these various classes if teachers intend to pair or group students of similar language abilities. Which suggests that students with a higher specialization receive more complicated materials and tasks than peers with a lower mastery linguistically.
- 4: One challenge that was stated in earlier called the age of the beginning of language learning and accessibility to the language of the students, which ranged significantly. As a consequence, the same courses were attended by learners with very distinct qualifications. While there are variations in linguistic skills in each CLIL classroom, the school should also strive towards sorting out those differences and introducing a shared norm to students of all ability levels. If I understood, by offering extra language support in classrooms called "language laboratories," the school tackled the situation of certain students' poor English language skills.
- 5: Difference in linguistic ability contributed, as mentioned before to the regular application of Urdu by teachers and students in the classroom. In the CLIL classroom, students' use of mother tongue is typically erratic and relatively difficult to manage. Subsequently, in this report, teachers stated that several conversations shifted accidentally to Urdu.
- 6: One main feature of the fruitful use of Urdu as a form of scaffolding language learning has still not been achieved, demonstrating the requirement for improvements and a manifested exercise of Urdu in the classroom.

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